

**THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL ISSUES OF TEACHING
FOREIGN LANGUAGES IN INSTITUTE OF PHARMACEUTICAL
EDUCATION AND RESEARCH**

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Abstract. The modern world needs competent and pharmaceutical professionals who are able to work in a multicultural society anywhere in the world. The purpose of this article is to determine the structure and content of the discipline "Foreign Language", which would contribute to a more conscious, active and motivated assimilation of the subject. The research methodology was IPER curriculum, programs of the discipline "Foreign language" for higher educational institutions and the existing literature on the research problem. To determine specific situations for the further use of a foreign (English) language, a focus group survey was conducted. The result of the study is the definition and justification of the structure of the practical course "Foreign Language" with the proposed topics and grammatical material, divided into workbooks (1st and 2nd terms). The authors of the article propose a course model consisting of two consecutive workbooks based on the needs of the trainees and the thematic content of the discipline. The proposed model of the practical course for teaching a foreign language will allow you to quickly form the universal competencies necessary for the future pharmacists and integrate into the professional community without any problems.

Key words: English language, IPER, pharmaceuticals, higher education, Hemis.uz, system of education, professional development of IPER students.

Introduction

Modern society is in government of constant change due to a number of factors, such as globalization, migration, informatization and digitalization, increased competition in the economy, and, finally, the Covid-19 pandemic. The latter has become a real test for all countries and industries, including the education system. The changed situation entails adaptation, modification and selection of approaches, methods and teaching aids, while the content of the discipline does not change, but remains fixed in accordance with the national standards of higher education, basic professional educational programs, curricula and work programs. The question arises - how to transform the discipline "Foreign language", so that in modern conditions and taking into account world trends, graduates of pharmaceutical areas of training can successfully integrate into a multicultural society.

Thus, the purpose of this article is to determine the structure and content of the course "Foreign Language" in higher pharmaceutical institute so that they correspond to the challenges of the current situation. Achieving this goal involves solving several problems: a) to study the current national educational standards of higher education; b) to analyze Uzbek and foreign approaches to the development of the content of the discipline "Foreign Language", c) to develop the structure and thematic planning of the course "Foreign Language" in higher educational institutions of the pharmaceutical profile, considering the needs of students. English is chosen as the basis, which is considered the international language of communication, the so-called ESP, since knowledge of English contributes to further academic and professional development, international communication, and scientific research.

The system of Uzbek higher education is determined by the National Educational Standards for Higher Education. In accordance with the National Educational Standard, a graduate of a higher educational institution must have a number of competencies in relation to English or another foreign language. Four most popular training programs at pharmaceutical directions were selected for analysis: Industrial Pharmacy and Pharmacy. Thus, future pharmacists should form a universal communicative competence, that is, be able to introduce modern communication technologies in foreign languages into educational and professional interaction. In addition, a graduate of this area of study should be able to apply modern communication technologies, can use all necessary terms from the field of pharmacy including in a foreign language, for academic and professional interaction and be able to analyze and take into account the diversity of cultures in the process of intercultural interaction.

As for the President Decree 5117 “On measures to bring the activities of popularization of learning foreign languages to a qualitatively new level in the Republic of Uzbekistan” is presented for discussion. According to this decree , students should be able to carry out professional communication in oral and written forms in a foreign language. Pharmaceutical students should be able to perceive the intercultural diversity of society in the socio-historical, ethical and philosophical contexts, manage their time, build and implement a self-development trajectory on based on the principles of lifelong learning of the foreign languages.

National educational standards are reflected in the work programs of academic disciplines. At IPER, students of the areas of study "Pharmacy and Industrial Pharmacy” study the discipline "Foreign Language" in the first and second semesters of the first year. The purpose of the discipline is to master the basics of oral and written forms of communication necessary for professional development, and their use as a means of communication. In the second

semester, future pharmacists study the Fundamentals of Professional Activity in a foreign language. This discipline is aimed at the formation of vocabulary and the development of professional skills and self-development. As for future industrial pharmacy specialists, they are offered an elective course "Scientific and technical English", related to the translation of pharmaceutical texts to master the skills of understanding written sources. Pharmacy students study the discipline "Foreign Language" for two semesters, striving to master oral and written forms of communication in order to use them as a means of communication and self-development.

The question often arises - why the level of a foreign language of graduates of higher educational institutions is not high enough? There may be several answers. So, according to S.P. Sinyavskaya, one of the reasons is "the lack of continuity in the teaching of foreign languages at school and at the university." The researcher says that in a foreign language class, the teacher has to repeat a certain amount of knowledge that first-year students did not master at school. The second reason the researcher considers is the insufficient number of hours devoted to the study of a professional foreign language. Another reason for D.S. Mamonkina considers the fact that, while studying in the first and second years, students are not fully aware of the need and possibilities of a foreign language in their subsequent professional activities. The study of English during this period is associated to a greater extent with the implementation of the curriculum. This idea is supplemented by a number of scientists who argue that in the first and second years students master highly professional vocabulary in English, not knowing it in Uzbek or Russian, which can lead either to an incorrect understanding of the lexical unit, or to forgetting it in the future. The researchers suggest continuing the development of a narrowly focused vocabulary and professional topics in senior courses or in parallel with the study of major disciplines.

In many parts of the world, English for Pharmaceutical Purposes is taught from the point of view of real situations, which means that the teaching of English is focused on a certain context and specific vocabulary. But more importantly, teaching Pharmaceutical English relies on developing communication, problem-solving and decision-making skills. At the end of the course, students should be able to understand professionally oriented texts about the latest developments in their field, practice and improve their oral and written skills, write scientific articles, participate in exchange programs and international scientific events. In other words, students must master functional language (standard phrases for communicating with patients, counseling, writing emails, etc.), language skills and systems.

The aims and outcomes of the various English language courses for medical students are generally the same. Only lexical content is subject to variations depending on specific professional areas, since each field (pharmacy and industrial pharmacy) has its own specifics. So, in Japan, pharmacy students after completing the course are able to: a) produce and perceive basic pharmaceutical phrases, understand the speech of their patients, ask their patients about their medical characteristics, explain some dental procedures, access and perceive information for native speakers published on the Internet, for example, when searching for and submitting applications to international medical conferences or journals (after the basic course), and b) understand and respond to technical dental phrases, create and give oral presentations on specific dental topics, communicate with medical employees through various means (after completing the advanced course).

In Uzbekistan, the focus is on interaction, as the future profession involves communication and context-specific activities. The course itself is based on task-based language learning, since learning is most effective when it is integrated with authentic tasks that are borrowed from everyday contexts. All materials are

duplicated on the electronic learning platform Moodle.org or hemis.uz. Typically, the lesson includes a preliminary stage (reading materials, watching videos, preparing presentations, drafting written assignments), classroom work (solving the task, report and discussion, analysis and evaluation, use of text, video and audio materials, feedback, writing summary, reviews, etc.), as well as the post-classroom stage (participation in discussions on the forum and chats, self-reflection, consultations with the teacher). For example, the groups are asked to develop a strategy to eliminate malaria in a remote village. In completing the task, students work with a wide range of materials, distribute materials and responsibilities among themselves, and try to find a possible solution to the problem. After discussing the proposed options, students jointly choose the best option.

In Pakistan, the course of English for Pharmaceutical Purposes is based on problem-based learning. To create real situations for the practice of communication, researchers suggest using information and communication technologies. At the same time, special attention is paid to medical terminology and the grammar-translation method. Thus, the study of the topic has a twofold structure: the first lesson focuses on the introduction and primary automation of vocabulary, the second lesson focuses on the application of new material in context, for example, filling out hospital forms and papers, using simple medical equipment, researching treatments, writing emails, discussing medical experience and more.

As part of the English for Pharmaceutical Purposes course, problem-based or problem-based learning is actively used. This method has both advantages (more detailed understanding of the issue, interaction with other disciplines, increased motivation and awareness of students) and disadvantages (time costs for the preparation of materials, maintenance costs, possible stress for both students and teachers). As a rule, the method is used to work in small groups,

which contributes to the development of tolerance and the ability to work in a team, teaches you to determine the rules of work, show initiative and mutual respect, and distribute responsibilities.

One of the variants of the problem-oriented method is medical cases. In medicine, the use of case studies is relevant, since they are aimed primarily at the patient and his problem and contribute not only to achieving the goals of a foreign language course, but also affect professionally oriented competencies. As part of solving cases, students are given the opportunity to update their knowledge of grammar, develop communication skills, learn the rules of word formation, prepare presentations, write research papers, develop teamwork skills, and so on.

In teaching a foreign language at different levels, the method of projects is actively used, higher pharmaceutical institutions are no exception. The project method affects various aspects, namely, in addition to the assimilation of educational material, it contributes to the development of creative potential, teaches to systematize acquired knowledge, analyze information, navigate the information flow, and activates the ability of independent and team work. However, there are a number of rules that must be followed in order for the project method to be effective, in particular, the subject of the project should always sound problematic, in the process of working on the project, the types of activities of students should vary, the results of the project should have practical, cognitive and theoretical value.

Another approach that is currently widely used in professionally oriented learning is content and language integrated learning (CLIL). The role of a foreign language in CLIL is unique, since it acts not only as a goal, but also as a means of teaching almost any discipline. CLIL is interpreted as an approach or method that combines the teaching of various disciplines with the simultaneous teaching of a foreign language. At the same time, students develop not only

language, but also communication skills that help to discuss the knowledge gained about science, art or technology with people of other nationalities.

The term CLIL itself originated in 1994 in Europe, although the first programs based on this technology appeared in Iraq much earlier. At the end of the 20th century, with the growth of interethnic relations, exchange programs and the interpenetration of cultures, the use of CLIL became a requirement of the time. In a modern interpretation, CLIL includes a variety of educational approaches such as "immersion", "bilingual and multilingual learning", "language showers" and "expanded language programs" and is quite flexible in use.

Recently, domestic researchers have published a number of works that consider the problems of CLIL and options for integrating it into the educational process of universities. So, L.L. Salekhova presented a model of bilingual teaching of mathematics based on an interdisciplinary competence-based approach. E.P. Shishmolina studied the influence of CLIL on the formation of the abilities of first-year students of pharmacy areas of training ("Pharmacy" and "Industrial Pharmacy") for self-organization and revealed an improvement in this indicator. T.A. Tancura considered the features of the CLIL application and described the implementation of a mixed model for teaching bachelors in the direction of "Pharmacy". This mixed model involves the teaching of language disciplines by institute specialists, and the implementation of specialty disciplines by native and subject teachers. According to N.V. Popova and co-authors, in modern universities CLIL technologies are most successfully implemented in the form of bilingual education based on general scientific and technical disciplines or in the process of teaching the discipline "Foreign Language in Professional Activities". A.A. Sirotova analyzed models of subject-language integration, identified their advantages and disadvantages, and determined the optimal model for use in a medical university. The model chosen

by the author was a “soft” model based on the thematic content of the disciplines taught. Training can be conducted by both subject teachers and linguists and is implemented through thematic and project immersions.

Along with the advantages of CLIL, the authors note a number of problems that need to be addressed. First, it is the qualification of teachers. Foreign language teachers should know at least the basics of the content aspect of the discipline of the specialty, and specialist teachers need to improve their language skills and master the methodology of teaching a foreign language. Secondly, in order to implement the CLIL technology, students need a B1 level according to Western European standards, which in reality does not always correspond to reality. And, finally, the creation of CLIL courses requires a lot of time and close interaction of teachers from different departments, which is currently a difficult task.

Materials and methods

In our study, we took the following steps: we studied the national standards of higher education, analyzed the goals and content of existing English language courses for pharmaceutical purposes in higher educational institutions, considered the language / speech aspects necessary for the professional activities of future doctors.

The method of analysis of scientific literature and sources on the problem, as well as the generalization of one's own pedagogical experience, made it possible to critically evaluate what was read, compare existing points of view on the problem, and develop the thematic structure of the course. To determine the attitude of students to the study of the English language and the areas of its practical application in their future careers, a survey was conducted, in which 175 first-year students of the IPER took part. The results of the survey were processed by statistical analysis and presented in digital form.

Results of the research

Awareness by students of their needs in learning a foreign language is a hallmark of professionally oriented education. Any professionally oriented training is based on the question: why does a student need a foreign language? That is why, before designing the course program, it is necessary to establish the needs for learning the language and analyze the linguistic features of their implementation.

In order to find out the communication needs of students in learning English, a survey was conducted. The students were asked the question: "Does a modern pharmacist need a foreign (English) language?" In the case of a positive answer, it was necessary to describe a specific situation in the application of knowledge. Since the second question was an open-ended question, the respondents could give several answers. The survey involved first-year IPER students enrolled in the areas of study "Industrial Pharmacy", and "Pharmacy".

According to the results of the survey, the majority of first-year students consider it necessary to use knowledge of English in their professional activities. They believe that "English is an international language, so a pharmacist must know it", "a modern pharmacist must speak English in order to meet international standards", "English language shows the highest level of professionalism". First-year students are ready to treat not only their fellow citizens, but also people of other nationalities (48.6%), provide emergency medical care to foreigners (21.1%), work in other countries (32.6%), consult with foreign specialists about their patients (4%). One respondent described a specific incident that occurred in class when an Indian student who spoke Uzbek poorly became ill, and an emergency pharmacist who did not speak English "could not understand what she was in pain." All these activities are inextricably linked with communication and intercultural interaction and emphasize the importance of developing communicative competence and intercultural interaction competence in the learning process.

More than a third of respondents plan to communicate with foreign colleagues, exchanging experience and knowledge (39.4%), as well as improve their skills by participating in international conferences, competitions (32.6%), reading scientific articles (18.9%) and additional specialized literature, which "have not yet been translated into Uzbek and, thus, receive a large amount of important and useful information" (27.4%). For the successful implementation of these activities, in addition to the formation of communicative and intercultural competence, it is necessary to develop the skills of self-organization and self-development. It is important for students to be able to independently build their own development trajectory and be able to organize their activities to achieve the set results.

The proportion of respondents who study English for general development (11.4%), travel (7.4%) or moving to another country (6.9%) is relatively small, which indicates pragmatism and a certain confidence of the respondents in the correct choice further profession.

The gap between those wishing to take part in international conferences (32.6%) and the publication of their own articles (9.7%) looks somewhat strange, which is usually an interconnected process, since participation in a conference implies the presentation of the results of one's research or experiment with further publication. Apparently, at this stage, the respondents present themselves as listeners, not speakers. In part, this may be due to the unpreparedness of first-year students for scientific activities, the lack of understanding of research activities and the lack of professional knowledge.

It is interesting to note that the proportion of students who believe that a modern pharmacist can do without knowing English is only 1.7% or three people. Moreover, one of them softens the negative answer, recognizing that: "The profession of a pharmacist does not require knowledge of the English language, however, in modern society, knowledge of English is quite a useful

skill." Such data are very different from the results of a survey conducted among first-year students of the pharmacy faculty of Tashkent Pharmaceutical Institute, where a third of the respondents showed no or insufficient motivation to learn a foreign language.

Scientists-methodologists see the structure of a foreign language course in different ways. For example, L.A. Gizyatov and N.F. Plotnikova believe that the course should consist of four aspects: 1) verbal communication with patients and colleagues, 2) written communication on professional topics (filling out case histories, making referrals to specialists, etc.), reading scientific texts on pharmaceutical topics, and 4) presentation of reports and presentations at conferences. Japanese researchers include two modules in the English language course for dentists, general and specialized. The course covers basic and advanced terminology (etymology and principles of terminology formation), as well as colloquial speech (communication between the dentist and the patient and interprofessional communication). Finnish authors offer a three-course English language program: a) a course focused on developing accuracy and fluency of speech, productive skills and medical vocabulary, b) a course focused on practical writing skills and c) a course focused on multicultural interaction with patients.

Indeed, the future professional activity of a physician involves interaction with different people. First, it is the interaction between doctor and patient. To do this, you need to learn how to ask and answer questions on various topics, formulate and express your thoughts, and overcome awkwardness in public speaking. In addition, such interaction includes casual and typical situations, discussions, facial expressions, gestures and interaction with representatives of other cultures.

Secondly, interaction with colleagues and specialists from other areas of training. That is, students must acquire the skills necessary to meet, interact and collaborate with colleagues in the medical field.

Thirdly, filling out various kinds of documents. Thus, researchers distinguish thirteen genres of written texts in the medical field, which can be divided into two groups: a) the development of reflective thinking (for example, self-assessment and peer assessment) and b) writing essays / reports (reports, annotated bibliographies, research proposals, care plans and portfolio, extracts and dissertations).

Fourthly, English allows you to get acquainted with the latest publications in the field of foreign pharmaceutical literature, expand the research base, conduct a comparative analysis of various phenomena, and more.

As for the grammatical content of the course, the researcher L.V. Dubenkova focuses on: 1) Present Simple (description of processes, diseases, conditions), Past Simple (medical history, previous hospitalizations, courses of treatment, symptoms) and Present Perfect (description of the onset of the disease, results of recent studies, discoveries), 2) passive voice, 3) modal verbs and abbreviations and abbreviations. The same opinion is shared by researchers L.A. Gizyatov and N.F. Plotnikov, supplementing the list with phrasal verbs and nouns of Latin and Greek origin with non-standard forms of plural formation, for example, nucleus-nuclei and others.

Having studied the theoretical information on the problem and the empirical data obtained during the survey, we determined that a foreign language course for pharmaceutical students should consist of three main modules. In the first year, students should focus on learning general pharmaceutical vocabulary and oral communication. Further, they improve pharmaceutical terminology and read texts of a professional orientation. At the third stage, students learn to produce their own texts and speak with them at conferences. In solidarity with

the researchers that at the beginning of the course it is often necessary to fill in the gaps in school knowledge, and the mastery of professional vocabulary occurs in the absence of knowledge in the subject of the specialty, we propose to distribute the discipline "Foreign Language" for three years with a gradual increase in complexity. Separate modules in the second and third (fourth) semesters of study should be added to the existing number of hours in the first year. Some authors note a decrease in the motivation to learn a foreign language in most students when moving to senior courses, but we explain this fact by the fact that not all future doctors associate their careers with scientific activities that involve active language skills. Therefore, the third module, intended for those who plan scientific and grant activities, can also be elective.

As a basis for the module, we take situations of language use that are oriented towards learning outcomes, determine their thematic content and the necessary language tools (vocabulary and grammatical structures). The second and third modules are also focused on the development of skills and abilities of various types of speech activity and involve learning autonomy and self-development. As a teaching method, a combination of forms and methods used in professionally oriented and subject-language integrated learning is proposed.

Discussion and conclusion

The technique of mastering terminological vocabulary does not depend on a narrow professional focus and involves the use of generally accepted stages, namely pre-text exercises (reading, listening, pronunciation, etc.) and post-text exercises (translation of individual words, phrases, terms, statements, formulation of their definitions, selection of synonyms and antonyms). Researcher F.A. Miskhodzheva, in order to expand the professional vocabulary, suggests working out industry vocabulary, pronunciation of English terms, and conducting a comparative analysis of terminological units and expressions in Uzbek and English.

In the second module, special attention should be paid to the selection of texts for reading. They should contain information about the latest achievements in the field of pharmaceutical, correspond to the research interests of the trainees and serve as an additional source of professional knowledge. The method of working with reading professional literature and academic writing can be as follows: a) read a clinical case, analyzing vocabulary and register, b) formulate questions to the patient in order to obtain clinically relevant information, formulate possible treatment options and make a query in the pharmaceutical database , c) find scientific publications relevant to the pharmaceutical case in databases of online libraries, d) analyze publications in order to determine the logic of the author and the structure of IMRAD, e) extract and structure characteristics from various scientific publications, f) evaluate the text of the article according to such linguistic features as academic register, syntax and semantics, interaction between the reader and the author, lexical and grammatical choice, and others, g) read a scientific article in which the “Methods” section has been deleted, try to reconstruct this section based on the main part of the article, and write the missing section.

Teaching a foreign language is usually not limited to the classroom and continues outside the classroom. Researchers note the productive use of such forms as student societies or circles, student scientific and practical conferences of various levels, subject Olympiads. The modern development of technologies allows remote participation in various international conferences, competitions and improve skills at seminars. In addition, students with a good knowledge of the language can participate in exchange programs and have the opportunity to do internships or internships at foreign universities or pharmaceutical institutions.

In conclusion, we note that the proposed modular training course for pharmaceutical students, distributed over three years, will allow the development

and activation of professional and academic skills and abilities and the formation of the necessary universal competencies. At the end of the course, students will be able to understand and apply pharmaceutical terminology, discuss and present professional information, read, understand and produce pharmaceutical texts of various types, as well as be aware of the responsibility for learning and project the trajectory of their further development. The acquired skills will allow them to be more confident in situations related to communication in the academic and professional fields, achieve great success in their careers and become a sought-after specialist not only in Uzbekistan, but also at the international level. It seems that the model of the course "Foreign Language" created by the authors can also be used as the basis for a similar modular course for students of other non-philological areas of study.

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